

The Role of Women in the Development of Uzbekistan

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Abstract: The article talks about women's participation in social and political relations, rights and freedoms, and the reforms implemented in this field.

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It is known that a number of normative legal documents have been adopted in our country aimed at protecting the rights and interests of women, legally strengthening their participation in state administration and political spheres. It is no exaggeration to say that this is the achievement of our national legislation, which is capable of creating justice laws and their enforcement mechanism, which can easily compete with the world community. In the words of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "... every woman should not be an ordinary observer, but also an active and proactive participant in the democratic changes taking place in the country ." [1] .

women 's participation in social and political relations, the fact that their rights and freedoms are ensured in practice is an important index of the development of states and democracy . Already, he emphasizes that the woman and her role in the life of the society have always been important and will continue to be important.

Along with the opportunities of women based on any social structure, their role is incomparable in the formation and development of the new generation. There are basic principles for guaranteeing equal rights and opportunities for women and men in society, which are legality, democracy, equal rights of women and men, non-discrimination on the basis of gender, openness and transparency. .

In the process of today's globalization, the place and role of women is more important than ever in the matter of forming an active civil position of the new generation in relation to any conditions. Therefore, the main content of the reforms is to support women to come up with new ideas and initiatives, to ensure their active participation in the efforts, changes and social-political processes implemented in our country. After all, if we say that glorifying the value of a person is first of all realized through respect and honoring women, honoring our honorable mothers, and valuing our munis sisters, we will be telling the same truth.

At this point, it is appropriate to talk about the history and development stages of gender equality in Uzbekistan. In particular, Problems related to the violation of gender equality have long existed in our history. It is known from history that in the East, the issue of respect for women was formed long before the West. Most sources say that gender equality began to take shape mainly in Western countries.

the 19th century - the beginning of the 20th century, the issues of the role and participation of women in the social and political life of the society were the focus of attention of Turkestan enlighteners. The role

of women in the society as educators of the nation's children was noticed even in those times. In the past, the work of our forefathers to increase the role of women in society, increase their educational potential, and ensure that they are socialized with men in the life of society on the basis of mutual equality, first of all, began with the reform of the field of education, the issues of women's education. It is a proof that it has been considered one of the urgent problems of this period. [2]

ensure gender equality and strengthen the place of women and girls as individuals in society into 3 periods:

First stage 1991-2000: Uzbekistan ratified the United Nations Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women on May 6, 1995, and it entered into force on August 18, 1995.

This Convention was adopted by the UN General Assembly in 1979. It sets forth the principles of women's rights applicable to all women in all fields in an internationally agreed legal imperative form. The main legal norm of the Convention is the norm prohibiting all forms of discrimination against women. In addition to demanding equal rights for women as compared to men, the Convention also sets out specific measures to ensure that women can enjoy the rights guaranteed to women everywhere.

The preamble of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women explains that despite the adoption of a number of treaties, women still do not have equal rights with men. Discrimination against women still persists in all countries.

This Convention, adopted by the General Assembly, was adopted in order to strengthen the provisions of existing international agreements aimed at ending discrimination against women. It describes specific areas of discrimination against women, such as political rights, marriage and family, and employment. In these and other areas, the Convention sets specific goals and measures that women should participate in to help build a harmonious society in which they enjoy the same rights as men, and thereby fully realize the human rights guaranteed to them.

In order to combat discrimination based on sex, the Convention advises States Parties to recognize the importance of women's economic and social contribution to the well-being of the family and the development of society in general. It specifically emphasizes that discrimination hinders economic development and the growth of prosperity. It also clearly recognizes the need to change perceptions and overcome heresies and customs based on negative views by conducting educational activities to recognize the equality of rights and obligations between men and women.

Another important feature of the Convention is the recognition of the need to achieve not only legal, but also factual equality, as well as the importance of adopting temporary special measures to achieve this goal.

The second stage Beginning of the 21st century : Normative legal documents on strengthening gender equality in Uzbekistan.

During this period, the government implemented national action plans and strategies to strengthen the participation of women in social, economic and political life.

In the political sphere: Civil service departments introduced a system of providing detailed information not only about the educational and professional training of the participants, but also about the gender ratio of the employees working in the relevant civil service positions. Consequently, a gender audit system was established in state bodies and organizations in order to assess compliance with legal requirements, including personnel policy, providing equal rights and opportunities for women and men. It involves a holistic approach to understanding and assessing gender equality.

Important decisions made with the participation of women ensure the success of the reforms that are being carried out in the direction of democratization of the society. In this respect, ensuring the rights and interests of women in our country and supporting them in every way is an important direction of the state policy.

As a result of practical work, 48 women deputies were elected to the lower house of the parliament

according to the results of last year's elections. This is 32 percent of the total number of deputies, and 25 percent in the Senate. For the first time in the history of Uzbekistan, the number of women in the national parliament reached a level consistent with the recommendations set by the UN. The parliament of our country has risen to the 37th place among 190 parliaments in the world in terms of the number of women

In the social sphere: It was proposed to cover the costs of vocational training of women and girls, to give additional benefits to working mothers, and to allow some women to retire at the age of 53. For example, part 1 of Article 4 of the Labor Code defines the minimum level of protection of labor rights of employees. This section ensures that all workers have basic rights and benefits such as fair wages, safe working conditions, and non-discrimination. These safeguards are designed to protect employees from exploitation and provide a framework for fair treatment in the workplace.

The third stage 2017- to the present period: women's rights and their place and role in society in New Uzbekistan.

, a number of reforms have been carried out to protect the rights and interests of women and improve their position in society. For example, the Law on Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men was passed by the Legislative Chamber on August 17, 2019, and approved by the Senate on August 23, 2019. It should be noted that the purpose of this law is stated in Chapter 1 of this law, which is to regulate relations in the field of ensuring equal rights and opportunities for women and men.

at Article 58 of our Constitution, "Men and women have equal rights. The issue of inequality between men and women and its solution has always been relevant in the society for thousands of years, and it is focused on the relevance of legal relations. In particular, as stated in Article 1 of the law on "Guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men" adopted by the Legislative Chamber on August 17, 2019 and approved by the Senate on August 23, 2019, the purpose of the law is to regulate relations in the field of equal rights and opportunities for women and men. The state provides women and men with equal rights and opportunities in managing society and state affairs, as well as in other spheres of society and state life. On this basis, the principles of "equality" and "social justice" reflecting gender policy have been incorporated into all laws and regulations. It should be noted that the law "On guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men" provides for the prevention of gender discrimination and the provision of equal participation of all in public administration. The Law "On Protection of Women from Harassment and Violence" is intended to end various forms of violence against women and includes mechanisms for the protection and assistance of victims. Special attention is paid to gender equality in the legal examination of draft laws and regulations.

In this regard, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 192 dated March 30, 2020 "On the approval of the regulation on the procedure for gender-legal examination of normative-legal documents and their drafts" was adopted, and now all normative-legal documents along with other criteria it was determined that gender legal expertise should also be conducted. During the expert examination, the normative legal documents of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Law "On guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men" and the issues of ensuring equal rights and opportunities for women and men are regulated. Particular attention is paid to compliance with the norms of other legal documents, mutual compatibility with each part of the principles of gender equality (equal rights, equal responsibility, equal opportunities, equal obligations) (practical equality in political, economic, labor and other social relations). Ensuring equal rights of women and men is one of the main requirements of the era. This is one of the main issues put forward by international organizations in recent years. Therefore, conducting a legal examination of the legal documents on the criteria of gender equality will undoubtedly create a basis for further improvement of normative legal documents and for our country to occupy a worthy place in the field of human rights protection in the world community.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Amendments and Amendments to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men" was adopted on December 15, 2022.

was developed based on paragraph 1 of the program of comprehensive measures to implement the strategy of achieving gender equality in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2021-2022 until 2030 .

This law introduces the concept of gender audit. According to it, Gender Audit is a systematic review to assess the impact of policies, programs and practices on gender equality. This includes:

1. **Assessment of compliance with the law: checking whether** government bodies and organizations comply with laws promoting equal rights and opportunities for women and men.
2. **Personnel policies:** Review hiring, promotion , and workplace policies to ensure they are fair and inclusive.
3. **Comprehensive approach:** analyzing how gender issues are integrated into all aspects of the organization's activities.
4. **Identification of defects:** identify areas where improvement is needed to increase gender equality.

Gender audits help organizations identify stereotypes and develop strategies to develop an inclusive culture that supports equal opportunities for all genders.

According to the three-year plan, the gender audit will be conducted by the Federation of Trade Unions of Uzbekistan within the framework of public control of state bodies and organizations.

determines the measures on the results of the review of the information and suggestions on the results of the gender audit and controls their implementation.

several additional powers of the republican commission on gender equality and family issues are being strengthened.

Conclusion. In the history of our nation, there were many virtuous women who gave birth to such people and inspired them to great deeds, among our great scholars and world-loving grandfathers. Even today, our women are selfless in raising their children in various fields and neighborhoods.

It should be noted that the main factor of achievements in the new stage of the development and progress of our country is directly related to the protection of the person and his rights and interests. For this reason, the main goal of democratic reforms is to ensure human rights and freedoms, to create peaceful and comfortable and decent living conditions for citizens, and to establish a fair legal state.

In recent years, significant work is being done to further strengthen the legal basis for ensuring equality between women and men in all fields. This can be seen in the example of the adoption of more than 42 legal documents. In particular, two important documents - "On guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men " and "On the protection of women from harassment and violence" are of great importance in this regard. It should also be noted that the new version of our Constitution, adopted by the will of our people, will be an important legal basis for raising reforms in this direction to a new level. After all, the opinion of our people was relied upon in the development of the new version of the Constitution. More than 40 percent of the proposals for the constitutional law came from women. This is a vivid expression of the worldview, thoughts and thinking of our people reflected in the new norms.

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